

Incidence of the yellow stem borer (YSB) on deep water rice in the Mekong delta, Vietnam

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In 1983, YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* damage as whiteheads was recorded at five sites in Mekong delta at different depths of floodwater. There was no significant difference in whiteheads

among various water depths and whitehead incidence was quite low (Table 1).

In 1984, whitehead damage on the 3 most popular varieties in Chau Phu was similar, about 5% whiteheads, with no significant difference among varieties. However, infestation found by dissecting 50 plants randomly collected for each variety at flowering, hard dough, and fully ripe stages were much higher: 30-44% (Table 2). *S*

Table 1. YSB incidence in deep water rice, Mekong delta, Vietnam, 1983.

Location ^a	Whiteheads (%)	Water depth (cm) at scoring	Highest water depth (cm)
An Giang province			
Chau Thanh	4.3	50	130
Chau Phu	4.6	60	160
Thoai Son	4.8	50	150
Dong Thap province			
Dong Cat	5.3	30	110
Thap Muoi	4.2	40	130

^aVarieties not recorded.

Table 2. YSB infestation in dissected plants at Chau Phu, An Giang, Vietnam, 1984.

Variety	Infestation at different growth stages and water depth					
	Flowering		Hard dough		Fully ripe	
	90 cm	110 cm	70 cm	90 cm	30 cm	50 cm
	<i>Infested plants (%)</i>					
Chet Cut	36	38	36	34	38	34
Nang Choi	32	36	32	38	36	44
Nang Tay Dum	30	38	36	32	36	40
	<i>Larvae (no./50 plants)</i>					
Chet Cut	10	8	4	5	5	5
Nang Choi	8	9	3	5	6	4
Nang Tay Dum	7	9	4	6	3	3
	<i>Pupae and pupal exuvate (no./50 plants)</i>					
Chet Cut	2	5	6	4	6	4
Nang Choi	3	3	7	5	4	6
Nang Tay Dum	2	4	3	4	5	7

Resistance of rice accessions to green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* and rice tungro virus (RTV)

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Rice accessions resistant to GLH were identified and reaction to RTV evaluated.

Using the seedling bulk test, 27 accessions were screened for GLH resistance in the greenhouse. Damage was scored at 6 d after infestation by the IRRI Standard evaluation system for rice (SES). Selected 15-d-old

resistant seedlings were inoculated with RTV. Seedling infection was recorded 20 d after inoculation. TN1 was the susceptible check for both vector and virus.

Of 27 rice accessions, IR24, IR29, IR54, ASD4, and Ponmani (CR1009) were found resistant to GLH (Table 1). Resistant accessions IR24, IR54, ASD4, and Ponmani and moderately resistant Vellai Ponni were tested for resistance to RTV. Only IR54 was resistant (Table 2). This suggests that resistance to the vector is independent of resistance to the virus. *S*

Table 1. GLH resistance of rice accessions, Tamil Nadu, India.

Accession	Damage rating ^a
IR24	3
IR29	3
IR54	3
ASD4	3
Ponmani	3
IR20	5
IR50	5
ASD11	5
ASD15	5
Ponni	5
Vellai Ponni	5
IR36	7
ASD3	7
ASD13	7
Co 42	7
Co 44	7
Punithavathi	7
Puduvai Ponni	7
IR42	9
ADT31	9
ADT36	9
ASD10	9
Co 40	9
Co 41	9
PY2	9
TKM6	9
TKM9	9
TN1 (susceptible check)	9

^aBy the IRRI SES.

Table 2. Reaction of selected rice accessions to RTV, Tamil Nadu, India.

Accession	Infection (%)	Evaluation ^a
IR54	20	R
Ponmani	40	MR
Vellai Ponni	50	MR
ASD4	70	S
IR24	80	S
TN1	100	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.